

Dividend policy as a multi-purpose mechanism; the case of conventional and Islamic banks before and after the 2008 crisis

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Abstract: Dividend policy and its association to firm value is still a concern for researchers. Empirical research provided evidence that it is relevant in various forms including signaling, pecking order, and agency. The aim of this study is to investigate the dividend policy of Islamic banks versus conventional banks in response to a major financial crisis. By studying the mixed banking industry of the Gulf Cooperation Council countries, known for negligible taxation systems, we provide evidence that conventional and Islamic banks use dividend payouts as a multi-purpose mechanism. At times of economic prosperity, conventional banks use them as signaling and pecking-order instruments, while it is used as an agency problem protection instrument during downturns. For Islamic banks, however, dividend policy is a pecking order mechanism before and after the crisis. Discussions on theoretical and empirical implications are provided.

JEL Classifications: G01, G21, G32

Keywords: Dividend policy, Islamic banks, financial crisis

Citation: Aldeehani, T. M. (2019). Dividend policy as a multi-purpose mechanism; the case of conventional and Islamic banks before and after the 2008 crisis. *Business and Economic Horizons*, 15(1), 37-59.

1. Introduction

Conventional and Islamic banks differ in the components of their capital structures. Conventional banks (CBs) receive deposits and treat them as liabilities. In this case, the depositor is a lender, and the bank is the borrower bearing all the risks. Therefore, to avoid interest payment default, CBs strike a balance in their asset-liability management. Islamic banks (IBs), on the other hand, receive deposits under profit and loss sharing agreements. According to these agreements, depositors are considered partners, implying a possible loss of part, or even all, of the amount deposited without legal obligation on the bank. Because clients bear the risks, IBs are tempted to take more risks with these deposits for the reward of making higher returns. Therefore, IBs presumably enjoy more profitability during times of economic prosperity. Conversely, at times of economic downturns they struggle more for recovery.

With this background, there is reason to believe that CBs and IBs differ in the way they set their financial policies including, among others, the dividend policy. There is also reason to believe that they responded differently to the recent global financial crisis that started in 2008. To provide evidence of these beliefs, the determinants of dividend policy of the two bank types were investigated before and during the time of the crisis. The paper addresses several important questions. What are the determinants of dividend policy

for CBs and IBs before and after the crisis? Did their purposes of paying cash dividends change in response to the crisis? If they did, what are they? And why did they change?

The results of this research should add more to the understanding of how dividend policy is set by CBs compared to IBs and provide theoretical and practical contributions.

The next section of the paper provides a discussion of the relevant literature on dividend policy focusing on the banking industry, and on the mixed banking systems in particular. The objective of the review is to develop our research conceptual framework and hypotheses which set out in a separate section. Following that, the scope of the data and the research methodology is addressed before presenting the results of the various tests and model estimations. The last section concludes with conclusions drawn from the research and some observations.

2. Literature review

In this paper, two strands of research relevant to the dividend policy of banks are recognized. The first is concerned with the relationship between firm value and its dividend policy that was initiated by Miller & Modigliani (1961). Their original proposition is that dividend policy is irrelevant to value. They claim that, if shareholders prefer an appreciation in stock market value, then profit should be retained by the firm to fund further growth. Therefore, the firm should pay no dividends. Alternatively, if they prefer cash, then they can always sell some of their shares. Again, no cash dividend distribution is necessary. They argue that shareholders are indifferent to the dividend policy of the firm. This argument implies that when firms pay, cut, increase or decrease cash payouts, stock traders do not respond and the stock market price remains unchanged. In the literature of corporate finance, this is called the “dividend irrelevance” theory. The first to criticize this theory were Lintner (1962) and Gordon (1963). They both believe that the Miller & Modigliani (1961) proposition is based on unrealistic assumptions. They believe that investors value a dollar of dividend today more than a dollar of price appreciation in the future. Miller & Modigliani (1961) disagreed and called this “bird-in-the-hand” theory. A third theory is called the “Tax preference” theory. It maintains that, where dividends are taxed more than capital gains, some investors prefer firms that retain profit to finance further growth. Because when they get cash dividend, a significant part of it will be deducted as taxes. This theory implies that an increase of dividend payout leads to lower value.

For those who believe that the dividend policy does matter to firm value (e.g., Barely et al., 1995; Fama & French, 1998; Dickens et al., 2003; and Bhattacharyya, 2007 for a review), it is crucial to investigate the determinants of this policy. This forms the second strand of the literature. To explain changes in dividend policy, the literature recognizes three main theories: the “clientele” theory, the “signaling” theory, and the “agency” theory. A review of the literature on these theories is summarized by Bhattacharyya (2007).

When Miller & Modigliani (1961) introduced their famous dividend-irrelevance proposition, it was criticized for being unrealistic as they ignored the effect of tax treatments. Opposing scholars (e.g., Peterson et al., 1985; Amihud & Murgia, 1997; Allen et al., 2000; Baker & Wurgler, 2004; DeAngelo & DeAngelo, 2006; and Komrattanapanya & Suntrarak, 2014) believe that dividend policy is relevant and that different clienteles have different preferences. Other researchers provided proofs of the signaling effects of

cash payouts. Bhattacharyya (1979) developed a signaling proposition based on the notion of information asymmetry. He argued that managers have deeper and more detailed information about the future cash flows of the firm and they convey this information by means of additional dividends as a signaling mechanism. A similar argument was made by Miller & Rock (1985), William (1988), and Bernheim & Wantz (1995). Advocates of the agency hypothesis believe that profitable firms with no further growth opportunities should pay a cash dividend to prevent executives from misusing in non-profitable investments. The hypothesis implies that accumulation of cash is associated with an increased agency cost. This notion is supported by Rozeff (1982), Easterbrook (1984), Moh'd et al. (1995), La Porta (2000), DeAngelo et al. (2004).

As the main driver of economic strength, the banking industry was extensively investigated in relation to dividend policy. For those who believe that dividend distribution is relevant to the value of the firm, it was important to understand how dividend policy is determined. It is even more important when there is a mixed banking market. This is particularly true for the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) region and other Islamic countries where most of the Islamic banks in the world coexist with their conventional counterpart. Many research attempts, within these mixed-banking markets, have been made to study the differences in dividend policies of IBs versus CBs. Hassan et al. (2003), for example, provided evidence of dividend signaling and agency cost effects in an interest-free banking system. By studying the dividend policy of the Malaysian mixed-banking market, Ameer (2008) provided evidence that the decision to cut or increase dividend is determined differently. He did not differentiate between IBs and CBs. A comparison between the dividend policies of IBs and CBs was later investigated by Eng, Yahya, & Hadi (2013). The dividend policy of IBs was found to be affected only by lagged dividends, implying the signaling effect, while CBs' dividend was found to be affected only by profitability.

Zameer et al. (2013) explored the determinants of dividend policy in the mixed-banking industry of Pakistan. They found that profitability, previous dividends, and ownership structure have a positive impact on dividend while liquidity had a negative impact. Size, risk, growth, and agency cost were found irrelevant to dividend policy. In his short paper on modeling dividend policy in the banking industry of the GCC region, Al-Ajmi (2010) did not differentiate between Islamic and conventional banks but provided mixed results about signaling and agency effects. He did, however, provide evidence of the effect of current earnings and previous dividend on cash payout policy. Athari et al. (2016) conducted a study of dividend policy in a dual-banking system covering some GCC countries in addition to Egypt and Jordan. They provided two agency explanation for the dividend payout. They found that IBs used dividends to mitigate risk and agency problem associated with accumulation of cash. Alternatively, CBs were found to follow the outcome model of dividend policy when dividend policy was more stable.

Al-Kayed (2017) compared the determinants of dividend policies of IBs to CBs. She found that IBs' dividend policy is affected by profitability, previous dividends, and leverage. She also found that for CBs, the dividend policy was affected by the same determinants in addition to liquidity and growth. The Agency theory was not tested.

Although some of the studies reviewed have covered the period before and after the 2008 global financial crisis, none of them has catered for its effect on bank dividend policy, especially when comparing between IBs and CBs. In the next section, we make use of the

reviewed literature to develop our conceptual framework, dependent and explanatory variables, and research hypotheses.

3. Conceptual framework, variables, and hypotheses

The research framework in this paper recognizes three main propositions to explain dividend decisions exercised by Islamic and conventional banks in a mixed banking system. With the assumption of the fundamental differences between the capital structures of IBs versus CBs, one would assume different dividend policies and determinants for the two types of banks based on the status of the economy (before and after the 2008 global financial crisis). To pursue the investigation, the model will be based on the three most established theories of dividend policy: the signaling, pecking order, and the agency effect theories. If we can provide evidence of the adoption of different forms of effects in different economic occasions, then banks are using dividend payouts for different purposes according to different needs.

As we are focusing on the GCC region where taxes are of a lesser concern, we excluded the clientele theory. We elected nine explanatory variables that were discussed in the literature, three variables to represent each theory. These variables are:

For signaling effect, we chose

- **Previous dividend** (div_{t-1}). This variable is calculated as the dividend per share in the previous year. When firms maintain a certain pattern in payouts despite variability in profitability performance, they signal their commitment to their shareholders (see for example Lintner, 1956; Miller & Modigliani, 1961; DeAngelo et al., 1992; Ben Naceur et al. (2006); and Al-Ajmi, 2010). Briston & Tomkins (1970) found that there was evidence of dividend policy stability in periods of a major change in the UK tax system. Eng, Yahya, & Hadi (2013) provided evidence of a positive association between payouts and previous dividend for IBs but not for CBs. Al-Kayed (2017) found a positive relation for CBs and IBs in Saudi Arabia. We, therefore, hypothesize that previous dividend positively affects dividend policy.
- **Future earnings** ($geps$). This is calculated as the change in earnings per share for the current year. There is ample evidence that the payment of dividends is seen by stock traders as a signal for future prospects of the firm. Miller & Modigliani (1961) argue that investors interpret change in dividend payout as a change in management view of future earnings. A statistically significant interaction effect between earnings and dividend announcement was reported by Kane et al. (1984). Nissim & Ziv (2001) reported similar results. Our hypothesis concerning this predictor is that future earning positively affects dividend policy.
- **Deposits** ($lndep$). It is calculated as the natural log of this year's deposits. Dividends signal on the future availability of cash (more deposits for banks). This variable could also be used to test the agency effect. The Miller & Modigliani (1961) argument on future cash flows could be applied to deposits for banks. Bhattacharyya (2007) provides a review discussion of this variable. Eng, Yahya, & Hadi (2013) did not support the hypothesis for either CBs or IBs. The hypothesis here is that deposits positively affect dividend policy.

For the pecking order effect, we chose:

- **Profitability (*eps*)**. This variable is defined as the year's earnings per share. Companies prefer internal funding over external funding to finance dividend distribution. So, higher profitability is associated with more dividend payouts. DeAngelo et al. (1992) argue that earnings do explain variation in dividend payouts. Various profitability proxies were employed by Barclay et al. (1995), Adedeji (1998), and Al-Malkawi (2007). Ameer (2008) provides evidence to support this hypothesis for Malaysian banks. He did not compare between CBs and IBs. Eng, Yahya, & Hadi (2013) did not support the hypothesis for either CBs or IBs. Al-Kayed (2017) found a positive relation for CBs and IBs in Saudi Arabia. For non-banking firms, Ben Naceur et al. (2006) provided evidence of the positive effects of earnings. The hypothesis here is that profitability positively affects dividend policy.
- **Investment (*inv**tota*)**. This is a proxy for a greater investment opportunity calculated as the percentage of investments on total assets. The relationship with dividend payouts is negative; when opportunities exist, they distribute less dividends. The hypothesis was supported by Al-Ajmi (2010) for most of the banks in the GCC region. However, he did not attempt to compare between CBs and IBs. Our hypothesis relevant to this predictor is that the investment ratio negatively affects dividend policy.

For agency effect, we chose:

- **Agency cost (*ac*)**. The capital ratio is used as a proxy for agency cost. Agency theory stipulates that higher agency cost indicates management misconduct and may be relevant to the accumulated cash when there are less profitable opportunities. The association to payout ratio could go either way. It could be positive supporting the argument that more cash encourages paying more dividends. Or, it could be negative supporting the argument that with management misconduct lesser dividends, than it should be, is paid out to shareholders. As in Berger & Patti (2006) and Pratomo & Ismail (2007). The hypothesis here is that agency cost negatively affects dividend policy.
- **Size (*ln**ta*)**. Large firms, typically measured by the natural log of their assets, generate more cash and the accumulated cash encourages management misconduct when profitable opportunities do not exist. The most of the existing literature on the size (a representative variable of agency) supports that larger firms should pay more dividends to overcome the agency problem. Eriotis (2005), Al-Malkawi (2007), and Denis & Osobov (2008) provided evidence that size is positively associated with higher cash payouts supporting the agency concept. Zameer et al. (2013) did not provide support for this hypothesis. Zameer et al. (2013) provided no support for this hypothesis. Our research hypothesis relevant to this predictor is that size positively affects dividend policy.
- **Fixed Assets Growth (*fatota*)**. This variable is calculated as the percentage of net fixed assets over total assets. If firms have no growth investment opportunities (investing in fixed assets) and still pay dividends, then there is a reason to believe they want to avoid agency problems. Although Zameer et al. (2013) did not support it as a hypothesis in his research, Eng, Yahya, & Hadi (2013) found a positive association for the case of CBs but not for IBs. Al-Kayed (2017) found a positive relation for CBs, but

not for IBs, in Saudi Arabia. Our hypothesis regarding this predictor is that fixed assets positively affect dividend policy.

- **Risk index (*ri*)**. The *ri* as proposed by Sinkey (1988) and Sinkey & Nash (1993) is defined as $(\sigma_{ROA} + \frac{E}{A})/\sigma_{ROA}$. We add this predictor as we believe that an increase of risk index, which implies a decrease in the level of general risk the bank is facing, should be positively associated with cash payouts. The argument here is that banks may use cash payouts to lower the risk leading to lower agency problems. Our hypothesis with this predictor is that higher risk index (lower level of risk) positively affects dividend policy.

For the dependent variable, we chose:

- **Dividend yield (*dy*)**. This variable is calculated as the current of divided per share over current price. Most of the research use the dividend payout ratio (current dividend divided by net income) as the dependent variable (see, e.g., Amidu & Abor (2006) and Komrattanapanya & Suntraruk, 2014).

A description of the variables is presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1. VARIABLES DESCRIPTION

VARIABLE	DESCRIPTION	PROXY	USED BY
<i>div_{-1t}</i>	Previously paid dividend	Percentage of previous dividend over price	Lintner (1956); Miller & Modigliani (1961); DeAngelo et al. (1992); Ben Naceur et al. (2006); Al-Ajmi (2010); Briston & Tomkins (1970); Eng, Yahya, & Hadi. (2013)
<i>geps</i>	Growth in future earnings	Change in earnings per share	Miller & Modigliani (1961); Kane et al. (1984); Nissim & Ziv (2001)
<i>indep</i>	Size of deposits	Calculated as the natural log of deposits	Bhattacharyya (2007); Eng, Yahya, & Hadi. (2013)
<i>eps</i>	Profitability	Calculated as net income over number of shares	DeAngelo et al. (1992); Barclay et al. (1995); Adedeji (1998); Ben Naceur et al. (2006); Al-Malkawi (2007); Ameer (2008); Eng, Yahya, & Hadi. (2013); Al-Kayed (2017)
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	Size of investments	Calculated as the percentage of investments over total assets	AL-Ajmi (2010)
<i>ac</i>	Agency cost	Calculated as the capital ratio	Berger & Patti (2006); Pratomo & Ismail (2007)
<i>ln_{ta}</i>	Size of bank	Natural log of total assets	Eriotis (2005); Al-Malkawi (2007); Denis & Osobov (2008); Zameer et al. (2013)
<i>fat_{tota}</i>	Fixed assets growth	Calculated as net fixed assets to total assets	Zameer et al. (2013); Eng, Yahya, & Hadi. (2013); Al-Kayed (2017)
<i>ri</i>	Risk Index	Calculated as the standard deviation of return on assets added to the equity ratio all divided by the standard deviation of return on assets	Sinkey (1988); Sinkey & Nash (1993)
<i>dy</i>	Dividend yield (dependent)	Percentage of current dividend per share over price	Amidu & Abor (2006); Ben Naceur et al. (2006); Komrattanapanya & Suntraruk, (2014)

4. Data and methodology

The data was collected using Bayanati financial & banking data from the Institute of Banking Studies in Kuwait. This is an online (Institute of Banking Studies, 2018) database for all companies listed in the Kuwait Stock Exchange. It also provides fundamental data for all banks in the GCC region. Initially, the attempt was to include all listed banks in the GCC region for the period from 2003 to 2016. Unfortunately, some were omitted because of either their short lives or lack of significant data. We also targeted strongly balanced panels, but this would have cut the sample even further. We ended up with a total of 76 banks, 50 of which are CBs and 26 are IBs.

Ultimately, the objective was to understand how the dividend policy of each bank type is set and to explore to what extent the 2008 global financial crisis affected how dividend policy is determined by each bank type.

The investigation starts with avoiding some of the common problems associated with causal model estimations. Therefore, we start with removing any multicollinearity among the proposed nine predictors for each bank type. This is done by estimating an OLS model regressing the dependent variable, dividend per share, on all nine predictors. The objective is to perform a variance inflation factor (VIF). Cutoff values of less than 10, 5, or even 2.5 are commonly used to eliminate variables with possible multicollinearity among predictors. We use a value of less than 2.5. We also use Fisher-type unit root method based on augmented Dickey-Fuller tests to test for data stationery. Variable remains when the null hypothesis of unit root existence is rejected. The Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data is selected as it handles unbalanced panel data. This is important for deciding on which method to use for testing differences in means. The student t -test is preferred when data is normal. Alternatively, the nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis equality-of-populations rank test must be employed.

To explore causal effects, the nature of the data compiled for this study calls for panel data analysis. This type of analysis takes two forms, the random effect form and the fixed effect for. We adopt the Hausman test to select the appropriate model. This is a test that analyses the coefficients resulting from estimating two OLS regressions, one with random effects and another with fixed effect. When the hypothesis of the test is rejected, a fixed effect model is more appropriate. Otherwise, the random effect model is more efficient, but the fixed effect model can still be consistent.

A general panel data fixed effect model may be written as following:

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + X_{it}\beta + u_{it} \text{ for } t = 1, \dots, T \text{ and } i = 1, \dots, N \quad (1)$$

Where y_{it} is the dependent variable for panel i at time t , α_i is the unobserved panel effect, X_{it} is $1 \times k$ explanatory variables matrix, β is the calculated $1 \times k$ coefficients matrix, and u_{it} is the error term.

The general panel data random effect model can be written as

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + X_{it}\beta + u_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where u_{it} is the between-entity error and ε_{it} is the within entity error.

5. Diagnostics and preliminary testing

We start our diagnostics by checking the multicollinearity among the predictors for the CBs dataset. The results of the OLS regression and VIF test are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2. RESULTS OF THE PRELIMINARY OLS REGRESSION AND VIF FOR CONVENTIONAL BANKS (CBs)

VARIABLE	COEF.	STD. ERR.	T	P> T	[95% CONF. INTERVAL]		VIF
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	.494052	.0324784	15.21	0.000	.4302682	.5578358	1.49
<i>geps</i>	.0004283	.0004727	0.91	0.365	-.0004999	.0013565	1.01
<i>lndep</i>	-.0012079	.0271931	-0.04	0.965	-.054612	.0521962	43.38
<i>eps</i>	.1639327	.0151275	10.84	0.000	.1342239	.1936414	1.52
<i>debtota</i>	.8141158	.9596008	0.85	0.397	-1.070431	2.698663	102.44
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	.0584972	.044357	1.32	0.188	-.028615	.1456093	1.44
<i>ac</i>	.9347817	.9575347	0.98	0.329	-.9457076	2.815271	99.50
<i>lnta</i>	-.0022739	.027766	-0.08	0.935	-.0568031	.0522554	37.58
<i>fatota</i>	.0295739	.8918612	0.03	0.974	-1.72194	1.781088	1.15
<i>ri</i>	.0008221	.0003175	2.59	0.010	.0001984	.0014457	1.17
<i>_cons</i>	-.8186654	.9618839	-0.85	0.395	-2.707696	1.070365	

The results indicate high VIF value for four predictors with possible collinearity. By excluding these variables, we end up with six possible predictors. Table 3 presents the results of re-estimating the model with the six predictors. The new VIF values indicate the problem is solved.

TABLE 3. RESULTS OF THE PRELIMINARY OLS REGRESSION AND VIF FOR CONVENTIONAL BANKS (CBs) AFTER REMOVAL OF PROBLEMATIC VARIABLES

VARIABLE	COEF.	STD. ERR.	T	P> T	[95% CONF. INTERVAL]		VIF
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	.4915182	.031974	15.37	0.000	.4287257	.5543107	1.45
<i>geps</i>	.0004483	.0004719	0.95	0.343	-.0004785	.001375	1.01
<i>eps</i>	.1615718	.0146366	11.04	0.000	.1328275	.190316	1.42
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	.0534518	.0375203	1.42	0.155	-.0202328	.1271364	1.03
<i>fatota</i>	.3403701	.8422678	0.40	0.686	-1.313726	1.994467	1.03
<i>ri</i>	.0009154	.0003068	2.98	0.003	.0003129	.0015179	1.09
<i>_cons</i>	-.0227208	.0168801	-1.35	0.179	-.055871	.0104293	

After the VIF examination, we end up with six predictors for CBs causal investigation. To decide on fixed or random effect modeling, we perform the Hausman test. This test requires running equations (1) and (2) and comparing their estimates. The results of this test are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4. RESULTS OF THE HAUSMAN TEST FOR CONVENTIONAL BANKS (CBs)

VARIABLE	COEFFICIENTS		(b-B) DIFFERENCE	sqrt(diag(V _b -V _B)) S.E.
	(b) fe	(B) re		
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	.3320877	.4915182	-.1594304	.0199423
<i>eps</i>	.0000308	.0004483	-.0004174	.0000959
<i>ri</i>	.1774903	.1615718	.0159186	.0124859
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	.1328597	.0534518	.0794079	.0736235
<i>fat_{tota}</i>	.7859691	.3403701	.445599	.7769467
<i>geps</i>	.0018788	.0009154	.0009635	.0011805

Notes: *b* = consistent under H_0 and H_a ; obtained from panel regression model estimator. *B* = inconsistent under H_a , efficient under H_0 ; obtained from panel regression model estimator. Test: H_0 : difference in coefficients not systematic. $\chi^2(6) = (b-B)'[(V_b - V_B)^{-1}](b-B) = 93.45$, Prob > chi2 = 0.0000.

The conclusion of the Hausman test is that it not possible to use the random effect option to the model panel data regression. The fixed-effect model is more appropriate. The results of this test show a χ^2 score of 93.45 and a *p*-value of 0.000 rejecting the null hypothesis to accept random effect.

Regressing *dps* on *geps*, *Indep*, *eps*, *debtota*, *inv_{tota}*, *ac*, *lnta*, and *ri* with the VIF test in the 1st run produced the VIF values for IBs dataset with an obvious multicollinearity problem in four predictors as shown in Table 5.

The 2nd run of the OLS regression after removing three of the four problematic variables, produced VIF values for the remaining predictors higher than the 2.5 cutoff point. We have ended up with seven potential explanatory variables for IBs causal investigation.

TABLE 5. THE VIF TESTS BEFORE AND AFTER THE REMOVAL OF PROBLEMATIC PREDICTORS

1 ST RUN: INCLUDING ALL VARIABLES			2 ND RUN: AFTER REMOVING HIGH VIF VARIABLES		
VARIABLE	VIF	1/VIF	VARIABLE	VIF	1/VIF
<i>ac</i>	127.50	0.007843	<i>div_{t-1}</i>	2.10	0.476941
<i>debtota</i>	122.56	0.008159	<i>eps</i>	1.94	0.516417
<i>lnta</i>	7.04	0.142083	<i>lnta</i>	1.43	0.698236
<i>Indep</i>	6.24	0.160272	<i>inv_{tota}</i>	1.18	0.845868
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	2.19	0.456677	<i>fat_{tota}</i>	1.10	0.909413
<i>eps</i>	1.94	0.515272	<i>ri</i>	1.09	0.915711
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	1.49	0.673159	<i>geps</i>	1.06	0.942521
<i>fat_{tota}</i>	1.26	0.796422	Mean VIF	1.41	
<i>ri</i>	1.20	0.833043			
<i>geps</i>	1.08	0.924165			
Mean VIF	27.25				

To decide on which effect model to adopt, again, we use the Hausman test for the IBs dataset in the manner we did with the CBs dataset. The results of this test are shown in Table 6.

TABLE 6. RESULTS OF THE HAUSMAN TEST FOR ISLAMIC BANKS (IBS)

VARIABLE	COEFFICIENTS		(b-B) DIFFERENCE	sqrt(diag(V _{b-V_B))) S.E.}
	(b) fe	(B) re		
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	.4521232	.5722702	-.120147	.0262
<i>geps</i>	-.0001974	-.0004162	.0002188	.0005405
<i>eps</i>	.1004533	.1290801	-.0286268	.0161353
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	.1439666	.0978009	.0461658	.0956167
<i>lnta</i>	.0113903	.0084274	.0029628	.0105557
<i>fatota</i>	-.0645429	-.1350706	.0705277	.6684216
<i>ri</i>	.0015018	.0000782	.0014236	.0010676

Notes: *b* = consistent under H_0 and H_a ; obtained from panel regression model estimator. *B* = inconsistent under H_a , efficient under H_0 ; obtained from panel regression model estimator. Test: H_0 : difference in coefficients not systematic. $\chi^2(6) = (b-B)'[(V_{b-V_B})^{-1}](b-B) = 22.00$, Prob>chi2 = 0.0025.

As indicated at the bottom of the Table 6, a χ^2 of 22.00 with a *p*-value of 0.0025 rejects the null hypothesis that the random effect appropriate. Therefore, for IBs dataset we would be using the panel data regression with fixed effect for causal investigation.

Table 7 presents the correlation matrix of the dependent variable and the potential explanatory variables for the CBs dataset.

TABLE 7. VARIABLES' CORRELATION MATRIX FOR CONVENTIONAL BANKS (CBs) DATASET

VARIABLE	<i>dps</i>	<i>div_{t-1}</i>	<i>geps</i>	<i>eps</i>	<i>inv_{tota}</i>	<i>fatota</i>	<i>ri</i>
<i>dps</i>	1.0000						
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	0.6920	1.0000					
<i>geps</i>	-0.0078	-0.0584	1.0000				
<i>eps</i>	0.6242	0.5337	-0.0027	1.0000			
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	0.0612	0.0495	-0.0090	-0.0122	1.0000		
<i>fatota</i>	-0.0300	-0.0397	-0.0209	-0.0279	-0.1517	1.0000	
<i>ri</i>	0.2883	0.2563	-0.0365	0.2336	0.0627	-0.0665	1.0000

A significant high positive correlation value between the dependent, *dps*, variable and the predictors; *div_{t-1}* and *eps* indicate potential positive causal effects. The relatively low correlation values among the potential independent variables confirm the independency of the variables and low collinearity. A summary statistics of the variables for CBs dataset are presented in Table 8.

TABLE 8. SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR CONVENTIONAL BANKS (CBS) DATASET

VARIABLE	OBS.	MEAN	STD. DEV.	MIN	MAX
<i>dps</i>	668	.1865023	.1979475	0	2.266229
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	617	.1934515	.199378	0	2.266229
<i>geps</i>	618	.6762588	11.2603	-8.423469	265.6776
<i>eps</i>	668	.4439088	.4232255	-2.867297	2.735895
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	668	.2707241	.1468702	.0287392	.9203521
<i>fatota</i>	668	.0092773	.006408	.0004146	.0827879
<i>ri</i>	668	25.2879	18.33361	-2.510582	123.5363

The zero minimum values for the *dps* and *div_{t-1}* designate nonpayment of cash dividend in some years. The high standard deviation of the investment to total assets ratio designates the volatility of the profitability indicator of CBs which is possibly caused by the global financial crisis during the period of the study. A further and more detailed description of the variables (Table 9) shows a comparison of the variables' means before and after the crisis.

Most of the variables exhibit a logical decline which can be explained by damaging consequence of the global crisis in 2008. However, we can observe that CBs exhibited a remarkable increase in the growth of earning per share ratio indicating a rapid recovery from the crisis.

TABLE 9. COMPARISON OF MEANS FOR CONVENTIONAL BANKS (CBS) DATASET

VARIABLE	CRISIS STATUS	MEAN	STD. ERR.	[95% CONF. INTERVAL]	
<i>dps</i>	Before	.2424889	.0161877	.2106991	.2742787
	After	.1539455	.0084091	.1374314	.1704595
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	Before	.2412436	.0128616	.2159856	.2665015
	After	.1664017	.0100051	.1467535	.18605
<i>geps</i>	Before	.253935	.1504851	-.041591	.549461
	After	.9167617	.705402	-4.685226	2.302046
<i>eps</i>	Before	.5906036	.0338167	.5241936	.6570136
	After	.3723012	.0182767	.336409	.4081934
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	Before	.2993945	.0105474	.2786813	.3201076
	After	.2466978	.0066143	.2337084	.2596871
<i>fatota</i>	Before	.009396	.0005038	.0084067	.0103853
	After	.0091001	.0002844	.0085416	.0096585
<i>ri</i>	Before	25.05314	1.266225	22.5665	27.53978
	After	25.23576	.8864034	23.49503	26.9765

The correlation matrix for the selected variable of the IBs dataset is presented in Table 10. The significant correlation values between the dependent variable *div_{t-1}* and two

predictors *eps* and *lnta* indicate possible causal effects. The low correlation values among predictors confirm variables' independence.

TABLE 10. CORRELATION MATRIX FOR ISLAMIC BANKS (IBS) DATASET

VARIABLE	<i>dps</i>	<i>div_{t-1}</i>	<i>geps</i>	<i>eps</i>	<i>inv_{tota}</i>	<i>lnta</i>	<i>fatota</i>	<i>ri</i>
<i>dps</i>	1.0000							
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	0.8079	1.0000						
<i>geps</i>	0.0491	0.0157	1.0000					
<i>eps</i>	0.6892	0.6676	0.1678	1.0000				
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	-0.0220	-0.0342	-0.0095	-0.1365	1.0000			
<i>lnta</i>	0.4035	0.4323	0.0346	0.3475	-0.3236	1.0000		
<i>fatota</i>	0.1145	0.1456	-0.0480	0.1075	-0.1373	0.2240	1.0000	
<i>ri</i>	-0.0586	-0.0901	0.0862	-0.0242	-0.1778	0.0908	0.1831	1.0000

Summary statistics of the selected variables for the IBs dataset is presented in Table 11. A high standard deviation value for the risk index indicates on the high variability in the level of risks, which is possibly a result of the financial crisis.

TABLE 11. SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR ISLAMIC BANKS' (IBS') VARIABLES

VARIABLE	OBS.	MEAN	STD. DEV.	MIN	MAX
<i>dps</i>	267	.104675	.152217	0	.7
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	241	.1091911	.157669	0	.7
<i>geps</i>	241	-.0788719	3.650523	-37.72849	19.74044
<i>eps</i>	267	.2389055	.3234104	-5.473449	2.292303
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	267	.1425336	.0977161	0	.6437339
<i>lnta</i>	267	8.656587	1.321699	5.242333	11.41535
<i>fatota</i>	267	.0135623	.013323	0	.075341
<i>ri</i>	267	20.98328	20.07043	1.582506	130.0466

A comparison of the means before and after the crisis for the IBs dataset is illustrated in Table 12. Unlike CBs, IBs exhibit a noticeable deterioration in the growth of their earning per share ratio after the crisis signifying a struggle to recover from the crisis. A simple comparison of the same ratio between the two types of banks, demonstrates that CBs exhibit better resilience. The decline in most of the values following the crisis is logical.

Before moving on to the causal models, we present two preliminary tests of normality and data stationary for the CBs dataset and IBs dataset. The results of the Shapiro-Wilk normality test for CBs dataset is depicted in Table 13.

The normality null hypothesis is rejected for all variables. The result implies that, for a comparison between means, a nonparametric rank test is more appropriate than the student *t*-test for the CBs dataset. Table 14 presents the results of the unit root test for data stationery, again, for the CBs dataset.

TABLE 12. COMPARISON OF MEANS FOR ISLAMIC BANKS (IBS) DATASET

VARIABLE	CRISIS STATUS	MEAN	STD. ERR.	[95% CONF. INTERVAL]	
<i>dps</i>	<i>Before</i>	.1610499	.0248299	.1121374	.2099623
	<i>After</i>	.0869177	.0092883	.0686207	.1052146
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	<i>Before</i>	.1505052	.0248887	.1014769	.1995334
	<i>After</i>	.093933	.0102524	.0737368	.1141293
<i>geps</i>	<i>Before</i>	.3667386	.1758421	.0203477	.7131295
	<i>After</i>	-.243444	.3147877	-.8635437	.3766556
<i>eps</i>	<i>Before</i>	.4782576	.0576427	.3647074	.5918077
	<i>After</i>	.1631106	.0148684	.1338215	.1923998
<i>invtota</i>	<i>Before</i>	.1431949	.0108466	.1218282	.1645616
	<i>After</i>	.139813	.0069763	.1260705	.1535555
<i>lnta</i>	<i>Before</i>	8.230411	.1550768	7.924926	8.535897
	<i>After</i>	8.989282	.0908015	8.810412	9.168152
<i>fatota</i>	<i>Before</i>	.0142881	.0020761	.0101983	.0183779
	<i>After</i>	.013389	.0009128	.0115909	.015187
<i>ri</i>	<i>Before</i>	17.97171	1.329654	15.35243	20.59099
	<i>After</i>	20.10519	1.457966	17.23314	22.97723

TABLE 13. RESULTS OF THE NORMALITY TEST FOR CONVENTIONAL BANKS (CBs) DATASET

VARIABLE	OBS.	W	V	Z	PROB.>Z
<i>dps</i>	668	0.83098	73.874	10.475	0.00000
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	617	0.83388	67.567	10.223	0.00000
<i>geps</i>	618	0.05801	383.699	14.438	0.00000
<i>eps</i>	668	0.83929	70.240	10.352	0.00000
<i>Invtotal</i>	668	0.92983	30.670	8.335	0.00000
<i>fatota</i>	668	0.75375	107.626	11.391	0.00000
<i>ri</i>	668	0.80632	84.653	10.807	0.00000

TABLE 14. RESULTS OF DATA STATIONARY TEST FOR CONVENTIONAL BANKS (CBs) DATASET

VARIABLE	Z-STATISTIC	P-VALUE
<i>dps</i>	-5.1015	0.0000
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	-4.2699	0.0000
<i>geps</i>	-17.3496	0.0000
<i>eps</i>	-6.0794	0.0000
<i>invtota</i>	-5.8474	0.0000
<i>fatota</i>	-5.9968	0.0000
<i>ri</i>	-4.3335	0.0000

The test rejects the null hypothesis that data contains unit root implying that data is stationary for all selected variable of the CBs data set. The results of the nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis-of-populations rank test is shown in Table 15. The table is useful for detecting the variables that changed significantly in response to the 2008 crisis.

TABLE 15. KRUSKAL-WALLIS EQUALITY-OF-POPULATIONS RANK TEST FOR CONVENTIONAL BANKS (CBS) DATASET

VARIABLE	STATUS	OBS.	RANK SUM	χ^2	PROB.
<i>dps</i>	<i>Before</i>	272	104122.50	28.746	0.0001
	<i>After</i>	396	119323.50		
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	<i>Before</i>	223	80378.00	29.080	0.0001
	<i>After</i>	394	110275.00		
<i>geps</i>	<i>Before</i>	223	77282.00	15.028	0.0001
	<i>After</i>	395	113989.00		
<i>eps</i>	<i>Before</i>	272	109136.00	54.871	0.0001
	<i>After</i>	396	114310.00		
<i>invtota</i>	<i>Before</i>	272	103355.00	25.486	0.0001
	<i>After</i>	396	120091.00		
<i>fatota</i>	<i>Before</i>	272	92008.00	0.175	0.6760
	<i>After</i>	396	131438.00		
<i>ri</i>	<i>Before</i>	272	89054.00	0.620	0.4310
	<i>After</i>	396	134392.00		

The Table 15 shows that except for the fixed assets ratio and risk index, the ranks of all remaining variables are significantly different indicating significant differences in means for CBs.

The results of the Shapiro-Wilk *W* test of normality for IBs (Table 16) shows that data of the selected variables are not normally distributed which, again, means that we cannot use parametric tests to compare means.

TABLE 16. RESULTS OF THE NORMALITY TEST FOR ISLAMIC BANKS (IBS) DATASET

VARIABLE	OBS.	<i>W</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>z</i>	PROB.> <i>Z</i>
<i>dps</i>	267	0.83194	32.299	8.111	0.00000
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	241	0.83463	29.040	7.823	0.00000
<i>geps</i>	241	0.35057	114.046	11.000	0.00000
<i>eps</i>	267	0.82710	33.230	8.177	0.00000
<i>invtota</i>	267	0.94230	11.089	5.616	0.00000
<i>lnta</i>	267	0.98836	2.238	1.880	0.00000
<i>fatota</i>	267	0.78765	40.811	8.657	0.00000
<i>ri</i>	267	0.72752	52.367	9.239	0.00000

The results of the Fisher unit root test (Table 17) indicate that only *div_{t-1}* variable contains a unit root for IBs dataset. According to this result, this variable should be removed as a predictor.

TABLE 17. RESULTS OF DATA STATIONARY TEST FOR ISLAMIC BANKS (IBS) DATASET

VARIABLE	Z-STATISTIC	P-VALUE
<i>dps</i>	-1.9207	0.0274
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	-0.9812	0.1632
<i>geps</i>	-12.3417	0.0000
<i>eps</i>	-5.1928	0.0000
<i>Inv_{tota}</i>	-1.4542	0.0729
<i>lnta</i>	-8.9637	0.0000
<i>fatota</i>	-2.9242	0.0017
<i>ri</i>	-10.7401	0.0000

Table 18 exhibits the results of the Kruskal-Wallis rank test which indicates that *div_{t-1}* variable is significantly different after the crisis. Similarly, *dps*, *geps*, *eps*, and *lnta* exhibit significant ranks differences.

TABLE 18. KRUSKAL-WALLIS RANK TEST FOR ISLAMIC BANKS (IBS) DATASET

VARIABLE	STATUS	OBS.	RANK SUM	χ^2	PROB.
<i>dps</i>	Before	82	12557.00	7.266	0.0070
	After	185	23221.00		
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	Before	65	8691.00	2.957	0.0722
	After	176	20470.00		
<i>geps</i>	Before	65	8952.00	5.122	0.0236
	After	176	20209.00		
<i>eps</i>	Before	82	14279.00	31.968	0.0001
	After	185	21499.00		
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	Before	82	10960.00	0.002	0.9614
	After	185	24818.00		
<i>lnta</i>	Before	82	8226.00	22.517	0.0001
	After	185	27552.00		
<i>fatota</i>	Before	82	10121.50	2.216	0.1366
	After	185	25656.50		
<i>ri</i>	Before	82	11843.00	2.158	0.1419
	After	185	23935.00		

6. Panel regression estimation

The causal fixed effect model represented in equation (1) will be estimated for three datasets. The first dataset contains conventional banks only, without considering the effect of the crisis. This is important for a comparison of these results with those after the inclusion of the crisis' effects. The second dataset includes only the panels representing CBs for the years before 2008. The third dataset includes the CBs for the period from

2008 to 2016. This is important to show the significant effect of the crisis when the periods of economic stability is separate from the period of economic instability. It may also provide evidence of how important it is to reflect such effects. Many financial studies were conducted using the time period covering the years 2008 and neglected the effect of the crisis.

The results of estimating the model for CBs using the 1st dataset is shown in Table 19. Two variables only (div_{t-1} and eps) are positively significant at the 5% significance level.

TABLE 19. RESULT OF ESTIMATING MODEL (1) FOR THE 1ST DATASET OF CONVENTIONAL BANKS (CBs) CBs

VARIABLE	COEF.	STD. ERR.	t	P> t	[95% CONF. INTERVAL]	
div_{t-1}	0.3320877	0.0376833	8.81	0.000***	0.2580701	0.4061054
$geps$	0.0000308	0.0004816	0.06	0.949	-0.0009150	0.0009767
eps	0.1774903	0.0192387	9.23	0.000***	0.1397016	0.2152791
$inv\ tota$	0.1328597	0.0826328	1.61	0.108	-0.0294478	0.2951673
$fatota$	0.7859691	1.1458890	0.69	0.493	-1.4647880	3.0367260
ri	0.0018788	0.0012197	1.54	0.124	-0.0005170	0.0042746
$_cons$	-0.0482333	0.0368321	-1.31	0.191	-0.1205790	0.0241124
R ² (between)	0.8426				Number of observations	617
F(6,561)	10.88				Number of panels	50
Prob.>F	0.0000					

Note: *** Significant at 1% level, ** significant at 5%, and * significant at 10%.

The results imply that the dividend policy of CBs is determined only by previous dividend and the current earnings per share. The question here is whether these results will hold when separating the data into two datasets: before and after the crisis. To answer this question, we re-estimated the model for the “before-crisis” dataset. The results of this estimation are presented in Table 20. The previous dividend effect did not hold for this dataset. Only the current earnings per share have a positive and significant effect of the dividend policy of conventional banks.

TABLE 20. RESULT OF ESTIMATING MODEL (1) FOR THE 2ND DATASET OF CONVENTIONAL BANKS (CBs)

VARIABLE	COEF.	STD. ERR.	t	P> t	[95% CONF. INTERVAL]	
div_{t-1}	0.0270311	0.1186488	0.23	0.820	-0.2071936	0.2612557
$geps$	-0.0011633	0.0055047	-0.21	0.833	-0.0120302	0.0097036
eps	0.1618791	0.0336563	4.81	0.000***	0.0954382	0.2283200
$inv\ tota$	0.0475939	0.1931634	0.25	0.806	-0.3337301	0.4289178
$fatota$	-2.1843960	2.4803760	-0.88	0.380	-7.0809060	2.7121150
ri	-0.0010567	0.0025095	-0.42	0.674	-0.0060107	0.0038972
$_cons$	0.1734069	0.0848220	2.04	0.042**	0.0059597	0.3408541
R ² (between)	0.2695				Number of observations	223
F(6,169)	8.98				Number of panels	48
Prob>F	0.0004					

Note: *** Significant at 1% level, ** significant at 5%, and * significant at 10%.

Now, the question is "What factor can predict dividend policy for the third dataset?". The results of the third run of the panel regression dividend model are depicted in Table 21. Four variables have significant positive effects. These are previous dividends, earning per share, investment ratio, and the risk index.

TABLE 21. RESULT OF ESTIMATING MODEL (1) FOR THE 3RD DATASET OF CONVENTIONAL BANKS (CBS)

VARIABLE	COEF.	STD. ERR.	t	P> t	[95% CONF. INTERVAL]	
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	0.1331740	0.0346830	3.84	0.000***	0.0649522	0.201396
<i>geps</i>	0.0002902	0.0003220	0.90	0.368	-0.0003432	0.000924
<i>eps</i>	0.2104372	0.0249786	8.42	0.000***	0.1613041	0.25957
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	0.1710216	0.0870423	1.96	0.050**	-0.0001912	0.342234
<i>fatota</i>	1.7996050	1.5483340	1.16	0.246	-1.2459790	4.84519
<i>ri</i>	0.0025853	0.0012116	2.13	0.034**	0.0002021	0.004969
<i>_cons</i>	-0.0706368	0.0400253	-1.76	0.078*	-0.1493668	0.008093
R ² (between)	0.7673				Number of observations	394
F(6,338)	19.78				Number of panels	50
Prob>F	0.0000					

Note: *** Significant at 1% level, ** significant at 5%, and * significant at 10%.

We follow the same procedures to investigate the dividend policy of IBs. The results of estimating the fixed effect panel regression for the complete dataset of IBs are presented in Table 22. A significant F value of 7.27 is indicative of good model specification.

TABLE 22. RESULT OF ESTIMATING MODEL (1) FOR THE 1ST DATASET OF ISLAMIC BANKS (IBS)

VARIABLE	COEF.	STD. ERR.	t	P> t	[95% CONF. INTERVAL]	
<i>geps</i>	-0.0015464	0.0018472	-0.84	0.403	-0.0051879	0.002095
<i>eps</i>	0.1842663	0.0300565	6.13	0.000***	0.1250135	0.243519
<i>inv_{tota}</i>	0.2628021	0.1308466	2.01	0.046**	0.0048539	0.52075
<i>lnta</i>	0.0285231	0.0131881	2.16	0.032**	0.0025243	0.054522
<i>fatota</i>	-0.0544825	0.9028336	-0.06	0.952	-1.8343100	1.725345
<i>ri</i>	0.0021673	0.0012704	1.71	0.089*	-0.0003371	0.004672
<i>_cons</i>	-0.2680603	0.1312568	-2.04	0.042**	-0.5268172	-0.0093
R ² (between)	0.4235				Number of observations	241
F(6,209)	7.27				Number of panels	26
Prob>F	0.0000					

Note: *** Significant at 1% level, ** significant at 5%, and * significant at 10%.

Three predictors have a positive significant effect on dividend policy. These are earnings per share, investment ratio, and size. The risk index is also positively significant at the 10% level.

Running the model for "before-crisis" dataset reveals weak model specification as indicated by the F value of 0.61 with prob>F = 0.7177 (Table 23).

TABLE 23. RESULT OF ESTIMATING MODEL (1) FOR THE 2ND DATASET OF ISLAMIC BANKS (IBS)

VARIABLE	COEF.	STD. ERR.	t	P> t	[95% CONF. INTERVAL]	
<i>geps</i>	-0.0095361	0.0164576	-0.58	0.565	-0.0427259	0.023654
<i>eps</i>	0.0695102	0.0735905	0.94	0.350	-0.0788992	0.21792
<i>invtotal</i>	0.1190729	0.5041191	0.24	0.814	-0.8975802	1.135726
<i>lnta</i>	0.0498091	0.0440894	1.13	0.265	-0.0391057	0.138724
<i>fatota</i>	-0.7941536	2.0391940	-0.39	0.699	-4.9065800	3.318273
<i>ri</i>	0.0022663	0.0037625	0.60	0.550	-0.0053215	0.009854
<i>_cons</i>	-0.3250799	0.3583253	-0.91	0.369	-1.0477120	0.397552
R ² (between)	0.6516				Number of observations	65
F(6,43)	0.61				Number of panels	16
Prob>F	0.7177					

The weak specification may be a result of a relatively small number of observations compared to 16 groups. For Islamic banks, the weak data sample is undermining any possible inference relevant to the period before the crisis. The reason for a smaller sample for the period before 2008 is the fact that there were fewer banks at that time. Gradually, the increase of the number of listed banks led to the larger sample size after 2008. This is reflected in the next run of the model.

The results for the “after crisis” dataset show that the earning per share predictor is the only predictor that is significant at the 5% level (Table 24). Though, two other predictors (growth in earnings per share and size) are significant at the 10% level.

TABLE 24. RESULT OF ESTIMATING MODEL (1) FOR THE 1ST DATASET OF ISLAMIC BANKS (IBS)

VARIABLE	COEF.	STD. ERR.	t	P> t	[95% CONF. INTERVAL]	
<i>geps</i>	-0.0021066	0.0011165	-1.89	0.061*	-0.0043135	0.0001
<i>eps</i>	0.3294499	0.0470530	7.00	0.000***	0.2364460	0.422454
<i>invtotal</i>	0.0882965	0.0868488	1.02	0.311	-0.0833668	0.25996
<i>lnta</i>	-0.0323122	0.0168495	-1.92	0.057*	-0.0656165	0.000992
<i>fatota</i>	-0.1171132	0.8354682	-0.14	0.889	-1.7684790	1.534253
<i>ri</i>	-0.0004156	0.0009566	-0.43	0.665	-0.0023064	0.001475
<i>_cons</i>	0.3207109	0.1619881	1.98	0.050***	0.0005293	0.640893
R ² (between)	0.4539				Number of observations	176
F(6,144)	8.40				Number of panels	26
Prob>F	0.0000					

Note: *** Significant at 1% level, ** significant at 5%, and * significant at 10%.

7. Discussion

We start our discussion with a summary of the causal model results as illustrated in Table 25.

TABLE 25. SUMMARY RESULTS OF THE CAUSAL MODEL

PREDICTOR	HYPOTHESIS SUPPORTED FOR <u>CBs</u>			HYPOTHESIS SUPPORTED FOR <u>IBs</u>		
	DATASET			DATASET		
	ENTIRE	BEFORE	AFTER	ENTIRE	BEFORE	AFTER
<i>div_{t-1}</i>	✓+***		✓+***			
<i>geps</i>						✓+*
<i>eps</i>	✓+***	✓+***	✓+***	✓+***		✓+***
<i>inv_{tota}</i>			✓+**	✓+**		
<i>lnta</i>				✓+**		✓+*
<i>fatota</i>						
<i>ri</i>			✓+**	✓+*		

Note: ✓ Hypothesis is supported; + Positive effect; *** Significant at 1% level, ** significant at 5%, and * significant at 10%.

We can understand from the outcome of this study that the dividend policy of CBs robustly confirms the pecking order hypothesis. Conventional banks seem to continue adopting the policy of preferring internal funding over external funding. The association of higher dividend payouts with the higher earnings is evident from the correlation relationship discussed earlier, and the significant causal effect of earning per share on cash dividends paid out to shareholders. Earnings per share variable is the only robust predictor that appeared to be statistically significant in all three data sets. The result confirms the pecking order effect evidence provided by Ameer (2008) in the study conducted on Malaysian banks. Although to a lesser extent, the previous dividend per share predictor can also be considered robust as it appeared to be statistically significant in two of the three datasets, the “entire-dataset” and the “after crisis” dataset. This result implies that CBs, despite the dramatic decrease in profitability following the crisis, were striving to signal their ability to maintain a pattern of cash payment for shareholders. This is an evidence of the adoption of a cash payout as a signaling instrument. It confirms previous earlier propositions made by Lintner (1956) and the evidence provided by DeAngelo et al. (1992) from their study on the NYSE. The final interesting result for CBs is the positive and significant effect of the risk index on dividend payouts. We note here that a higher risk index implies a lower level of risks associated with lower agency problem. What we may understand from this result is that, and in response to the global financial crisis, CBs adopted the agency effect with cash payouts to mitigate management misconduct at times of economic instability. The result is consistent with the arguments made by Rozeff (1982) and DeAngelo & DeAngelo (2004).

For IBs, earning per share is the only robust predictor with a significant positive effect on dividend policy. It appeared statistically significant for the “entire” dataset and the “after crisis” dataset. The argument here is that IBs in the GCC region are following the pecking order to distribute cash dividends to shareholders. They prefer internal funding over external funding. Looking at the “entire” dataset, we can observe that IBs use dividend

payouts to signal the strength of their financial positions. This is confirmed by the significant and positive effect of the investment ratio on dividend policy. Our explanation for the positive effect is that IBs use dividend payouts to signal their ability to pay a cash dividend in the presence of investment opportunity which also requires funding. This latter result contradicts with the evidence of negative association provided by AL-Ajmi (2010) for the same region. The positive and significant effect of bank size on dividend policy for the “entire” dataset implies that IBs are gradually adopting payment of cash dividends as a mechanism to mitigate management misconduct and avoid potential agency problems. This result is consistent with the arguments made by Zameer et al. (2013) but contradicts the evidence provided by Al-Kayed (2017) who found a positive association for CBs only.

8. Research limitations

This study suffers from two obvious limitations. The first one is the, relatively, small sample of IBs compared to that of CBs. This limitation is tied to the shorter time series of some of the IBs included in the sample which may undermine the confidence in the results generalization relevant to IBs in the GCC region. The second limitation is the fact that it focuses on a regional market instead of considering the wider global market. Investigating this subject at the global market level would, certainly, increase the confidence to generalize on the results beyond the regional market.

9. Concluding remarks

Considerable literature has been accumulating following Miller & Modigliani (1961) controversial argument on dividend policy. Since then, the majority of this literature provided evidence on its relevance to firm value. Many forms of dividend effects were progressively developed, including, but not limited to, signaling, pecking-order, and agency. Guided by these forms of effects, we developed a conceptual framework to investigate the applicability of these forms in a mixed banking industry before and during a major economic downturn. The main proposition was that, if CBs and IBs differ in their capital structures they must be different in the way they set their dividend policies. We adopted a panel data regression model with fixed effect to test this proposition.

The results reveal that, at times of economic prosperity (before the 2008 crisis), CBs used dividend payout as a signaling instrument and a pecking-order instrument. At times of economic instability (after the 2008 crisis), they used it as an agency-protection instrument. A logical interpretation of this result is that CBs realized that agency problems during the time of economic instability is more damaging to the value of the firm calling for more controlling measures. For IBs, the results indicate that dividend policy is used in the form of pecking-order mechanism irrelevant to the status of the economy. It is interesting to note that, only at the time of economic stability, IBs used dividend payout as an instrument against agency problems. A possible interpretation of this result is that IBs have realized the agency problem during this period and acted sooner to mitigate its effects. The absence of this instrument after the crisis may be due to the significant decrease in IBs' growth of earnings compared to CBs as discussed earlier.

The main conclusion of the results is that dividend policies of CBs and IBs are determined differently. Dividend policy for each bank type differed according to economic status and the individual needs of bank types. The change in the form-of-effects implies that dividend policies are used as a multi-purpose mechanism. That is the form of effect changes as the need changes. One important theoretical implication of this argument is that the multi-purpose notion developed in this paper may be a practical interpretation of the so-called “*dividend puzzle*” of Black (1976).

One final note on the results is that, for both bank types and irrelevant to economics status, earnings per share is the only robust predictor of dividend policy serving the purpose of pecking-order effect. This result indicates that, when it comes to considering new investment opportunities, banks in the GCC region, prefer internal funding over external funding.

The results of this paper show that dividend payouts represent an important instrument that can be informative to investors about the future perspectives of the firm. They also serve as a growth funding instrument and a protection instrument against agency risks. To maintain the objective of value maximization, and depending on their particular needs, bankers should know which form of dividend policy to adopt. For instance, in certain occasions, dividend policy can serve only as a signaling instrument, while in other occasions it should be adopted as an investment funding instrument or as a protection mechanism against management misconduct.

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